

Is Fermat's Least Time Principle Equivalent to a Least Information Approach? Part 3

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In Part 2, we discussed a duality which seems to exist in the derivation of Snell's law, namely that one may use either conservation of momentum in the direction parallel to the n_1 - n_2 index of refraction surface, or minimize time (according to Fermat's Principle). We argued that the traditional view of minimizing time is really based on minimization of information following the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. One may minimize $t/(1/E)$ in time or $x/(1/p)$ in space independently and obtain the same result. Given that E is the same in both the n_1 and n_2 regions it appears as if one minimizes time, but given $x/(1/p)$ one sees that it is information $x/(1/p)$ which is minimized in x space and $t/(1/E)$ in time, we argue.

Here, we re-examine this problem in terms of information. In Part 2, we noted that special relativity (Lorentz transformation specifically) follows from considering a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$, t from a frame moving at $-v$. Then: $E = \gamma(v) m_0 c^2$ and $p = \gamma(v) m_0 v$ as well as $x' = \gamma(v) x - \gamma(v) v t$ and $t' = \gamma(v) t$. To find $\gamma(v)$ one may use the deterministic Newton's second law $F = dp/dt$ (in connection with work $\int F \cdot dr$). It is this equation which gives rise to both the idea of conservation of momentum and the special relativistic transformation and hence Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. Both of these, however, do not carry the full information of the problem as $x=vt$ is an extra piece of information. As a result, we suggest that trying to solve a problem using only conservation of momentum or $-Et+px$ (information minimization) involves a partial information approach (which is exactly what statistical mechanics does). This is the main idea we try to develop in this note.

Determinism Based on $F = dp/dt$

It is said that Newtonian mechanics is deterministic, but we ask: What specifically does that mean? We suggest that it means that one must know:

$x(t)$, the solution of $F = dp/dt$ ((1))

It is true that $F = dp/dt$ leads to the idea of conservation of momentum if F and $-F$ (action and equal reaction) are at work, but this is not the complete picture of what happens. The complete deterministic picture is knowledge of $x(t)$ as F is acting. As a result, one may solve a problem using conservation of momentum (and possibly kinetic energy), but this might give rise to multiple solutions as one is not following the particle through $x(t)$. A partial description of a particle, we argue, is like a statistical one in which one may consider probabilities etc.

We further note that one may use $F = dp/dt$ to derive $\gamma(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, the special relativistic function. One first considers a rest particle with mass m_0 , at $x=0$, t from a frame moving with $-v$. This leads to:

$E = \gamma(v) m_0 c^2$ $p = \gamma(v) m_0 v$ $x' = \gamma(v) x - \gamma(v) v t$ and $t' = \gamma(v) t$ ((2))

$g(v)$ is unknown, but we showed in Part 1, that it may be obtained using $F=dp/dt$ and the notion of work $\int F dx$. Thus, one obtains the Lorentz transformation and then the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et+px \quad ((3))$$

We argue, however, that ((3)) is not the complete information as $x=vt$ is an equation which is independent of ((3)). If one wishes to solve a problem using ((3)), this involves using partial information (i.e. might be linked to a statistical point of view). We consider this in detail using Snell's law.

Refraction and Snell's Law

To solve refraction in a completely deterministic manner, one would need to describe the interaction of a photon with atoms at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction. This is not done as it is complicated. Rather, two approaches, which are partial information ones, may be used. We called this the particle-wave duality approach to Snell's law in Part 2.

First, one may use conservation of momentum along the n_1 - n_2 junction (along the x axis) at $y=0$. Then:

$$p_1 \sin(\theta_1) = p_2 \sin(\theta_2) \quad p_1=p \cdot n_1 \quad p_2=p \cdot n_2 \quad \text{and } \theta \text{ is measured from the } y \text{ axis} \quad ((4))$$

We stress that this is a partial information approach to solving the problem. One does not see the exact details of the interaction which Newton's determinism would require.

In Part 2, we suggested a second partial information approach using the Lorentz invariant

$$-Et+px \quad ((5))$$

We suggested that one has two types of information:

$$\text{Time } t / (1/E) \quad \text{or} \quad \text{Space } x / (1/p) \quad ((6))$$

One minimizes either one or the other to get the same result. In the time case, E is the same in the n_1 and n_2 regions and so we argued that the minimization then appears to be for time, i.e. the traditional Fermat's Least Time Principle approach. Using ((6)), however, one sees that the solution is really about minimizing information which is a statistical approach.

One may show that ((6)) leads to Snell's law, as done in Part 2, but here we wish to discuss why one should use such an approach in the first place.

We first argue that $-Et+px$ and conservation are both partial information approaches linked with the deterministic equation $F=dp/dt$. In other words, one starts off with the notion of incomplete

information and tries to see if one may solve a problem without considering all of the details present. We argue that this is the very notion of a statistical approach to solving a problem.

We next consider a particle which moves in a straight line. From Newton's point of view, there is no interaction and so the particle should move in its initial direction. From an information point of view, if there is no specific information present, one would also assume that the particle moves in a straight line. A photon should move in a straight line in n_1 and also in n_2 . It is possible, however, that these are different straight lines. In such a case, how can one use information to solve the problem?

In Part 2, we suggested the minimization of information given by ((6)). At first this appears to be a global approach as one starts with $x=0, y_0$, an n_1 - n_2 interface at $y=0$ and a hit point of x and a final point of $L-x, -y_0$. One may set

$$y_0 = dy \quad ((7))$$

and so make this a tiny fluctuation problem and not a global one. The main idea is to try to solve the problem without knowing the exact physical interactions which occur between the photon and the atoms. This involves considering fluctuations which do not change the solution. In other words, one does not consider a fully deterministic approach, but rather an approximate one. One may consider a solution with a particular x and then shift to $x+dx$ in such a manner that the information (given by p_x from the Lorentz invariant) does not change to first order. This is a statistical approach to solving the problem. If such an approach does not work, then the physical system seems to be very sensitive to fluctuations in that one cannot even use x versus $x+dx$ and a deterministic approach might be needed. As it is, the partial information approach seems to work as:

$$d/dx \{ p_1 \sqrt{y_0 y_0 + x x} + p_2 \sqrt{y_0 y_0 + (L-x)(L-z)} \} = 0 \text{ yields Snells' law } ((8))$$

We suggest that this is a statistical approach because one needs to consider fluctuations in x and that $1/p$ (or more correctly \hbar/p) is a unit used to compute information in x . As noted in Part 2, this may be extended into a probability theory using the complex probability

$$\exp(-Et+ipx) \quad ((9))$$

It is ultimately the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ which gives rise to the idea of $1/E$ and $1/p$ as information units in t and x .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that Newtonian mechanics, namely $F=dp/dt$, is deterministic and gives rise to $x(t)$. $x(t)$ provides full information, but not all problems are solved in full detail. That does not mean that one cannot obtain partial information solutions, but these might be linked with probability. For example, one might try to solve a collision problem, even in Newtonian mechanics, using conservation of momentum and energy. This might lead to many solutions

and one might have equal product probability for each. In the Snell's law case, one may use conservation of momentum along the n_1 - n_2 interface surface, but we stress that this is a partial information solution. It does not show exactly the interaction of the photon with the atoms. We also suggest that $-Et+px$ may also be used to solve the problem as a partial information approach. This Lorentz information does not explicitly contain $x=vt$, and so even though $F=dp/dt$ may be used to find $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, $-Et+px$ is not a full information expression. Using it alone seems to be a partial information (or statistical approach). We suggest that to solve the 2-D refraction problem, one needs to consider a fluctuation dx in the x point at which the photon hits the n_1 - n_2 junction, as such a fluctuation should not change an information calculation. If it does, the physical system is too sensitive for an approximate partial information solution, we argue. Fortunately, using $d/dx \{ p_1 \sqrt{y_0^2 + x^2} + p_2 \sqrt{y_0^2 + (L-x)^2} \} = 0$ yields Snell's law by consider $1/p_1$ and $1/p_2$ as being information units in space in n_1 and n_2 . It is special relativity (namely $-Et+px$) which allows for these units).